

Complexing behaviour of 4-benzylideneamino-3-methyl-1-piperidino-methyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-thione towards some transition metals

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The complexes of bivalent Cd, Hg, Zn, Ni, Co, Ru and Pd with 4-benzylideneamino-3-methyl-1-piperidinomethyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-thione have been prepared and characterised.

The present paper discusses the preparation of complexes of bivalent Cd, Hg, Zn, Ni, Co, Ru and Pd with 4-benzylideneamino-3-methyl-1-piperidinomethyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-thione (BMPT). The complexes have been characterised on the basis of analytical, magnetic, thermal, conductance and spectral data.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results (Table 1) show that Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pd^{II} form MCl₂ type complexes, while Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Ru^{II} from MCl₂ type complexes with two molecules of coordinated water. All the complexes are diamagnetic with the exception of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes. The observed magnetic moments of Ni^{II}-BMPT and Co^{II}-BMPT complexes are 3.14 and 5.02 B.M. respectively, as ex-

pected.

The molar conductance values of the complexes (4.7–31.0 Ω⁻¹ mol⁻¹ cm²) indicate that they are non-electrolytes and neutral in nature. The thermogravimetric analysis of the complexes of BMPT showed that the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Ru^{II} complexes contain coordinated water molecules. A loss in weight is observed at 100–200°. The number of water molecules coordinated is found to be two in the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Ru^{II} complexes. All other complexes are stable upto 200° and decompose in two major steps.

The ground state of Ru^{II} in octahedral field is ¹A_{1g} and the excited states corresponding to t_{2g}⁵ e_g configuration are ³T_{1g}, ³T_{2g}, ¹T_{1g} and ¹T_{2g} in the increasing order of energy. Hence four transitions can be expected – two spin-forbid-

Table 1. Analytical and electronic spectral data of the complexes*

Complex	Metal % : Found/ (Calcd.)	λ _{max} cm ⁻¹	Assignment	10 Dq	B	β
[Cd(C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₅ S)Cl ₂]	22.56 (22.54)					
[Hg(C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₅ S)Cl ₂]	34.16 (34.18)					
[Zn(C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₅ S)Cl ₂]	14.43 (14.48)					
[Ni(C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₅ S)Cl ₂ . 2H ₂ O]	12.21 (12.20)					
[Co(C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₅ S)Cl ₂ . 2H ₂ O]	12.26 (12.24)	8230 ^a	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)			
		18518	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ A _{2g} (F)	10288	963.0	0.86
		20618	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (F)			
[Ru(C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₅ S)Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O]	19.28 (19.31)	16690	¹ A _{1g} → ³ T _{1g}			
		20360	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g}	22195	251.8	0.41
		24390	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g}			
[Pd(C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₅ S)Cl ₂]	21.58 (21.59)	19880	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ A _{2g}			
		20512	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1g}			
		24691	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ E _g			

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses. ^aCalculated.

den and two spin-allowed. The low spin d^6 system is less complicated so far as charge transfer excited states are concerned because no states from L-M transition are possible at low energies¹. In the electronic spectra of high-spin octahedral complexes of Co^{II} , three transitions can be expected from the ground state ${}^4T_{1g}(F)$. Two transitions are observed in the electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complex corresponding to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$. Palladium usually forms square-planar complexes. The ground state for the low spin d^8 system is therefore ${}^1A_{1g}$. Three spin-allowed states ${}^1A_{2g}$, 1E_g and ${}^1B_{1g}$ as well as three spin-forbidden states ${}^3A_{2g}$, 3E_g and ${}^3B_{1g}$ will be in the ligand field excited states. Therefore, three spin-allowed and three spin-forbidden transitions can be expected for such systems. However, not all the possible transitions can really be observed because some of them are masked either due to charge transfer or due to inter-ligand interactions. From the band positions, the values of $10 Dq$, B and β have been calculated. The values are within the range of those found for other octahedral complexes which justify the assignments. The bands actually observed and the assignments of transitions are presented in Table 1.

The infrared spectra of the ligand and its complexes are quite complicated owing to the overlap of various bands. However, the systematic shifts in the positions of a few ligand bands on complexation give some clue to the bonding scheme of the complexes.

The ligand molecule only have two major bonding sites – the thione sulfur and the azomethine nitrogen. At 1650 cm^{-1} a band is observed in the spectrum of ligand, which is assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ of $\text{N=N-CH-C}_6\text{H}_5$ group. In the spectra of the complexes this band is red-shifted² slightly, indicating coordination of the nitrogen of this group. The ligand band at $\sim 840 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=S) is shifted towards $780+10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes. This indicates coordination of C=S group with the metal ion. The band due to $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ of water molecules are present at 3400 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes. Also new but weak bands are observed in

the region $350\text{--}500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes due to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ coupled with other modes of vibrations.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR or chemically pure grade. The ligands used were prepared by the reported procedures. The metal complexes were prepared by a general method. To a hot aqueous solution of the metal(II) chloride (2 mmol), a hot solution of the ligand BMPT (2 mmol) was added and the mixture was refluxed for ~ 3 h. The resulting complexes were washed with hot water, alcohol and ether, and then dried in a hot air-oven.

Sulfur, chloride and metals were determined by standard methods³. C, H and N were analysed at R.S.I.C. of C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Magnetic susceptibility was determined using a Gouy balance at room temperature using mercury tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as the standard. Molar conductance of the complexes in $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ DMF solution was measured using an Elico conductivity meter. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out in a Mettler TA 4000 instrument (at KREC Suratkal) at the rate of $20^\circ/\text{min}$. The absorption spectra (DMF) were recorded on a Beckman DU-6 spectrophotometer, and ir spectra (KBr/CsI) on a Perkin-Elmer 1330 spectrophotometer at R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Madras.

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References

1. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968; C. J. Ballhausen in "Coordination Chemistry", ed A. E. Martell, Van Nostrand, New York, 1971, Vol. I
2. R. Singh, J. P. Srinivastava and L. K. Mishra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1969, **15**, 805.
3. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 4th ed., Longmans, London, 1978.